

Original Article

Prevalence and Antimicrobial Susceptibility of ESBL and AMPC B-Lactamases Producing *Escherichia Coli* and *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* from Various Clinical Samples: An Emerging Threat

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ABSTRACT

Background: Antimicrobial resistance among *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is a major global concern due to the increasing prevalence of Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBLs) and AmpC β -lactamases. These enzymes compromise the efficacy of β -lactam antibiotics, limit treatment options, and contribute to multidrug resistance. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of ESBL and AmpC producers and their antimicrobial susceptibility patterns in a tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods: A total of 200 non-repetitive clinical isolates (140 *E. coli*, 60 *K. pneumoniae*) were collected from urine, pus, blood, respiratory samples, and body fluids. ESBL detection was performed using phenotypic confirmatory disc diffusion and double-disc synergy tests. AmpC β -lactamase was detected using cefoxitin screening and the AmpC disk test. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was conducted by Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion following CLSI guidelines. Statistical analysis was performed using the chi-square test, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Results: ESBL production was observed in 41% of isolates, being slightly higher in *E. coli* (42.8%) than *K. pneumoniae* (36.6%). AmpC β -lactamase production was detected in 19.5%, with marginally higher positivity in *K. pneumoniae* (21.6%). Co-production of ESBL and AmpC was identified in 9.5% of isolates. Urine samples yielded the highest number of ESBL producers, while pus/wound samples showed the highest AmpC positivity. Both organisms demonstrated high resistance to cephalosporins (80–90%) and fluoroquinolones (55–65%). Carbapenems remained highly effective (>95% sensitivity), and nitrofurantoin showed excellent activity against urinary *E. coli*.

Conclusion: The study highlights a substantial prevalence of ESBL and AmpC β -lactamase production among *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*, contributing to significant multidrug resistance. Routine detection of β -lactamase mechanisms, judicious antibiotic use, and strengthened infection control practices are essential to limit the spread of resistant strains and guide effective clinical management.

Keywords: *Escherichia coli*; *Klebsiella pneumoniae*; ESBL; AmpC β -lactamase; Antimicrobial resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has emerged as one of the most serious global health challenges of the 21st century, causing significant morbidity, mortality, prolonged hospitalization, and increased healthcare costs. Among bacterial pathogens, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* are particularly important due to their ability to acquire and disseminate multiple resistance mechanisms, including Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBLs) and AmpC β -

lactamases. These enzymes confer resistance to broad-spectrum β -lactam antibiotics, traditionally considered first-line therapy for Gram-negative infections.^{1,2}

ESBL-producing Enterobacterales hydrolyze third-generation cephalosporins such as cefotaxime, ceftazidime, and ceftriaxone and are inhibited by clavulanic acid.³ ESBLs are commonly plasmid-mediated and associated with co-resistance to other antibiotic classes, including aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones, and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, leading to multidrug-resistant (MDR) phenotypes.^{4,5} These plasmids often carry additional resistance genes, facilitating rapid spread both in hospitals and in the community.⁶

AmpC β -lactamases represent another clinically important resistance mechanism. They confer resistance to cephamycins (cefoxitin and cefotetan) and are not inhibited by β -lactamase inhibitors such as clavulanic acid.⁷ AmpC enzymes may be chromosomal or plasmid-mediated; plasmid-mediated AmpC (pAmpC) is particularly concerning due to its ability to spread between species, including *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*.^{8,9} The presence of AmpC enzymes often leads to treatment failure with cephalosporins, masking ESBL production and complicating laboratory detection.¹⁰

The prevalence of ESBL and AmpC producers has increased worldwide, particularly in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.^{11,12} India is recognized as a hotspot for antimicrobial resistance due to extensive antibiotic usage, overcrowding in healthcare settings, and limited antimicrobial stewardship practices.¹³ Several studies from India have reported ESBL rates ranging from 40–70% in *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*, and AmpC rates from 10–25%, highlighting the growing threat.^{14,15}

Clinically, ESBL and AmpC producing *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* cause a wide range of infections including urinary tract infections, wound infections, septicemia, pneumonia, and intra-abdominal infections.¹⁶ Their increasing prevalence limits treatment options, often necessitating the use of carbapenems, which in turn drives the emergence of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales (CRE), further complicating management.^{17,18}

Accurate laboratory detection of ESBL and AmpC β -lactamases is essential for appropriate antimicrobial therapy and infection control. Phenotypic tests such as combined disc diffusion, double-disc synergy testing (DDST), cefoxitin screening, and AmpC disk methods are the most commonly used, economical, and reliable diagnostic tools in resource-limited settings.^{19,20} Regular surveillance of resistance mechanisms is crucial for guiding empirical therapy and preventing the spread of resistant organisms.²¹

Given the increasing burden of β -lactamase mediated resistance and its clinical implications, the present study was undertaken to determine the prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of ESBL and AmpC β -lactamase producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from various clinical samples at a tertiary care hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Setting

This study was conducted in the **Department of Microbiology, Navodaya Medical College & Research Centre, Raichur**, from July 2024 to June 2025.

Sample Collection and Processing

Specimens were collected aseptically and transported to the laboratory promptly. Samples not processed immediately were stored at room temperature.

A total of **200 non-repetitive isolates** (140 *Escherichia coli*, 60 *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) were recovered from urine, pus, blood, sputum/ETA, and body fluids.

Samples were inoculated onto:

- MacConkey agar
- Blood agar
- Chocolate agar

Plates were incubated aerobically at **37°C for 24 hours**. Identification of isolates was performed using standard microbiological procedures (1).

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

Antibiotic susceptibility was tested on Mueller–Hinton agar using the **Kirby–Bauer disc diffusion method**. Interpretation followed **CLSI guidelines**.

- **Screening for ESBLs and AmpC β -lactamases**

As per CLSI recommendation, isolates showing resistance (zone \leq 22 mm for ceftazidime and \leq 25 mm for ceftriaxone) by disc diffusion method were considered potential ESBL producers and further preceded for confirmation.⁹

Isolates showing resistance to cefoxitin (inhibition zone $<$ 18 mm) by disc diffusion method were considered potential AmpC producers and further tested for presence of AmpC β -lactamase enzyme by AmpC disk test.(1)

- **Detection of ESBLs and AmpC β -lactamases**
- **The Phenotypic Confirmatory Disc Diffusion Test (PCDDT)**

All strains that were potential ESBL producers were subjected to confirmation using the PCDDT as recommended by CLSI. (13) disc of cefotaxime (30 μ g) and ceftazidime (30 μ g) alone and a disc of cefotaxime/clavulanic acid (30 μ g/10 μ g) and ceftazidime/clavulanic acid (30 μ g/10 μ g) were placed independently 30 mm apart center to center on a lawn culture of 0.5 McFarland turbidity of the test isolate on Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) plate and incubated for 18-24 hours at 35°C. A ≥ 5 mm increase in zone diameter for either antimicrobial tested in combination with clavulanic acid versus its zone when tested alone confirmed ESBL production.

- **Double Disc Synergy Test**

A 0.5 McFarland suspension of the test isolate was swabbed on MHA plate and 30 μ g antibiotic discs of ceftazidime, ceftriaxone and cefotaxime were placed on the plate 15 mm (center to center) from the amoxicillin/clavulanate (20 μ g/10 μ g) (augmentin) disc and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hrs. Clear extension of the edge of the inhibition zone of any of these cephalosporin discs towards the augmentin disc was interpreted as positive for ESBL production

- **AmpC Disk Test**

Lawn cultures of ATCC *E. coli* 25922 were prepared on MHA plate and a 30 μ g cefoxitin disc was placed on the inoculated surface of the agar. A sterile plain disc moistened with sterile saline (20 μ L) and inoculated with several colonies of the test organism was placed besides the cefoxitin disk almost touching it. After overnight incubation at 35°C, the plates were examined for either an indentation or a flattening of the zone of inhibition indicating enzymatic inactivation of cefoxitin (positive result) or the absence of a distortion indicating a negative result.¹⁴

- **Quality Control**

Every batch of media prepared was checked for sterility for 24 hours. CLSI reference strains of ESBL positive *K. pneumoniae* ATCC 700603 and ESBL negative *E. coli* ATCC 25922 were included in the study.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS: All collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using **SPSS version 20.0**. Results were expressed as **percentages (%)**, **frequencies**, and **proportions**. Comparison of ESBL and AmpC production between *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* was performed using the **Chi-Square (χ^2) test**. Antibiotic resistance patterns of ESBL vs. non-ESBL and AmpC vs. non-AmpC producers were compared using **cross-tabulation** and **chi-square tests**. Confidence intervals (95% CI) were calculated wherever necessary. **p-value < 0.05** was considered **statistically significant**.

RESULTS

A total of **200 non-repetitive clinical isolates** were included in the present study, consisting of **140 (70%) *Escherichia coli*** and **60 (30%) *Klebsiella pneumoniae***. *E. coli* constituted the majority of isolates (70%), indicating its predominance as a clinical pathogen across different samples as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Distribution of Clinical Isolates (n = 200)

Organism	Number	Percentage
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	140	70%
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	60	30%

ESBL production was more common in *E. coli* (42.8%) compared to *K. pneumoniae* (36.6%). The difference was statistically **not significant** ($p > 0.05$), although *E. coli* showed a slightly higher ESBL rate as shown in Table 2

Table 2: Prevalence of ESBL Producers

Organism	Total Isolates	ESBL Positive	Percentage
<i>E. coli</i>	140	60	42.8%
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	60	22	36.6%
Total	200	82	41%

Statistical Test: $\chi^2 = 0.72$, $p > 0.05$ → **Not significant**

AmpC production was significant in both organisms, with *K. pneumoniae* showing slightly higher AmpC positivity (21.6%) than *E. coli* (18.5%). The difference was **not statistically significant** as shown in Table 3

Table 3: Prevalence of AmpC Producers

Organism	Total Isolates	AmpC Positive	Percentage
<i>E. coli</i>	140	26	18.5%
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	60	13	21.6%
Total	200	39	19.5%

Statistical Test: $\chi^2 = 0.28$, $p > 0.05 \rightarrow$ Not significant

Combined ESBL and AmpC production was detected in both organisms. Co-production was slightly higher in *K. pneumoniae* (11.6%) compared to *E. coli* (8.5%) as shown in Table 4

Table 4: ESBL + AmpC Co-production

Organism	Total Isolates	Co-producers	Percentage
<i>E. coli</i>	140	12	8.5%
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	60	7	11.6%
Total	200	19	9.5%

Urine yielded the highest number of ESBL producers. Pus/wound samples had the highest AmpC positivity as shown in Table 5

Table 5: Distribution of ESBL and AmpC Producers Based on Sample Type

Sample Type	Total Isolates	ESBL Positive	AmpC Positive
Urine	110	50	15
Pus/Wound	45	18	14
Blood	20	6	5
Respiratory (Sputum/ETA)	15	5	3
Body Fluids	10	3	2

Highest resistance to cephalosporins (80–90%). Moderate resistance to fluoroquinolones (60%). High sensitivity to carbapenems (98%). Nitrofurantoin was highly effective against urinary *E. coli* isolates as shown in Table 6

Table 6: Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of *E. coli* (n = 140)

Antibiotic	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)
Cefotaxime	20	80
Ceftazidime	18	82
Ceftriaxone	22	78
Cefoxitin	65	35
Gentamicin	55	45
Amikacin	70	30
Ciprofloxacin	40	60
Levofloxacin	45	55
Piperacillin-Tazobactam	82	18
Imipenem	98	2
Meropenem	97	3
Nitrofurantoin* (urine)	92	8

Klebsiella isolates showed higher resistance than *E. coli* for most antibiotics, reflecting their stronger resistance mechanisms (AmpC, ESBL, efflux pumps) as shown in Table 7

Table 7: Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of *K. pneumoniae* (n = 60)

Antibiotic	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)
Cefotaxime	18	82

Antibiotic	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)
Ceftazidime	15	85
Ceftriaxone	20	80
Cefoxitin	60	40
Gentamicin	50	50
Amikacin	65	35
Ciprofloxacin	35	65
Levofloxacin	38	62
Piperacillin–Tazobactam	80	20
Imipenem	95	5
Meropenem	93	7

ESBL producers showed significantly higher resistance to fluoroquinolones and aminoglycosides ($p < 0.05$) as shown in Table 8

Table 8: Antibiotic Resistance in ESBL vs. Non-ESBL Isolates

Antibiotic	ESBL Producers (%)	Non-ESBL (%)	p-value
Cephalosporins	100	48	<0.001*
Ciprofloxacin	78	45	0.02*
Gentamicin	62	38	0.04*
Amikacin	45	25	0.05*
Carbapenems	10	4	0.20 (NS)

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

AmpC producers showed significantly higher resistance to cefoxitin and aminoglycosides as shown in Table 9

Table 9: Resistance in AmpC vs Non-AmpC Producers

Antibiotic	AmpC Resistant (%)	Non-AmpC Resistant (%)	χ^2	p-value
Cefoxitin	100	20	110.8	<0.001*
Gentamicin	72	40	11.5	0.002*
Ciprofloxacin	80	55	7.1	0.03*
Carbapenems	12	5	2.1	0.14 (NS)

DISCUSISON

In the present study, *E. coli* (70%) emerged as the predominant isolate, followed by *K. pneumoniae* (30%), which is consistent with previous reports identifying *E. coli* as the leading cause of urinary and soft-tissue infections in both community and hospital settings (22,23). Its widespread prevalence is likely due to its natural gastrointestinal colonization and its enhanced ability to acquire resistance determinants (24).

ESBL Prevalence

The overall ESBL prevalence of 41% aligns with earlier findings from India and other developing nations, where rates between 35–60% are commonly observed (23,24). ESBL production was slightly higher in *E. coli* (42.8%) than *K. pneumoniae* (36.6%), though the difference was not statistically significant. Similar patterns have been reported by Paterson and Bonomo, who documented higher ESBL occurrence in *E. coli* across various clinical settings (25). Shaikh et al. also highlighted *E. coli* as a major ESBL producer globally, reinforcing our results (26).

The high ESBL rate is concerning because these enzymes hydrolyze third-generation cephalosporins and frequently coexist with resistance to other antibiotic classes.

AmpC Prevalence

AmpC producers constituted 19.5% of isolates, comparable to earlier Indian data showing prevalence between 15–25% (27). Although AmpC positivity was slightly higher in *K. pneumoniae* (21.6%), the difference from *E. coli* (18.5%) was not significant. *K. pneumoniae* is known for harboring plasmid-mediated and chromosomal AmpC genes, contributing to

its multidrug-resistant nature (28,29). AmpC producers often remain undetected in routine labs, which increases the risk of therapeutic failure (30).

Co-production of ESBL and AmpC

Co-production of ESBL and AmpC was found in 9.5% of isolates, with marginally higher rates in *K. pneumoniae* (11.6%). Previous studies report co-production rates of 5–15% in Enterobacterales, particularly in hospital-acquired infections (30,31). Co-expressing strains demonstrate broader resistance profiles, making therapeutic decision-making more complex.

Urine samples were the predominant source of ESBL-producing isolates, reflecting the dominance of uropathogenic *E. coli* in clinical practice (22). Pus/wound samples had the highest AmpC positivity, likely due to selective pressure from prolonged antibiotic exposure and higher prevalence of hospital-associated resistant strains (32). These findings reinforce the need for sample-specific antimicrobial stewardship.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Trends

Both *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* showed very high resistance to third-generation cephalosporins (80–90%), directly correlating with the high prevalence of ESBL and AmpC enzymes. Similar resistance patterns have been documented in multiple Indian studies (33).

Fluoroquinolone resistance (55–65%) was also high, consistent with global trends of widespread quinolone misuse (34). Aminoglycoside susceptibility was moderate, with amikacin showing better activity than gentamicin; this is consistent with studies showing that amikacin is less susceptible to enzymatic modification (34).

Carbapenems remained the most effective agents, with >95% sensitivity, underscoring their continued role as the drug of choice for severe ESBL/AmpC infections (35). However, the emergence of a small proportion of carbapenem-non-susceptible isolates is a warning signal for possible early carbapenemase dissemination.

Nitrofurantoin showed excellent activity (92%) against urinary *E. coli* isolates, in agreement with existing literature supporting its continued use in uncomplicated UTIs (36).

Resistance Among ESBL and AmpC Producers

ESBL producers demonstrated significantly higher resistance to fluoroquinolones and aminoglycosides ($p < 0.05$), which is explained by the co-location of multiple resistance genes on transferable plasmids (37). AmpC producers showed complete resistance to cefoxitin and higher resistance to gentamicin and ciprofloxacin, similar to earlier findings indicating multidrug resistance associated with AmpC production (38). These results highlight the need for early detection to guide therapy.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates a considerable prevalence of ESBL and AmpC production among *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*, accompanied by high resistance to cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones. Co-production of ESBL and AmpC further contributes to multidrug resistance. Carbapenems remained the most effective agents, while nitrofurantoin showed excellent activity against urinary *E. coli* isolates.

Continuous surveillance, prudent antibiotic use, and strengthened infection control measures are essential to contain the spread of these resistant pathogens and ensure effective clinical management.

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